

The Effect of the Mid-Day Meal (MDM) Programme on the Student's Academic Achievement at the Primary Level after Covid-19

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Abstract:- The study attempt to evaluate the effect of the Mid-Day Meal programme on the academic achievement of primary students in the Tufanganj area in the Coochbehar district. To collect data 25 schools and 500 students are selected randomly and gather data according to the results registered. These are compared between two years. The Govt of India introduced a national nutrition programme on 15th August 1995.MDM scheme is outstanding in terms of the academic achievement of students.

Keywords:- Mid-Day Meal, Result Register, National Nutrition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Free and compulsory universal education is a fundamental right, According to the 21A Act or the Right to education act, Universal Elementary Education from 6years to 14 years is compulsory. It provides to prohibit child labour and get equality and empathy without considering the caste creed and tribe. The India Government introduced the National Programme (NP-NSPE) on the 15th of August 1995. 8-12gr of protein 300 calories and 100 gr food grain are entertained to every 6-14 years age group. Rs 4.97 per head is considered for this scheme and The central govt. And state Govt. Contribute ratio is 60:40.Privileged Primary education has been demanding some special nutrition for future achievement. Hunger in mid-day becomes a barrier to academic achievement.

So, hot-cooked quality foods are needed to merge into the education system. Education influences Nationalism, economics, lifestyle and the development of a country.

UNESCO (data analysis 2019) found approximately 8% of primary age group students 787 million do not go to school during the pandemic situation or after. That means 58.4 million drop-out primary schools only. we should revive every NGOS, Private or public incentive and initiatives to overcome pry. Education.

Govt. of India and the state Govt. share their contribution to Mid Day Meal (MDM) 60:40.

Now PM- POSHON, Pradhan Mantri Poshon Shakti Nutrition is renamed MDM. It is more mechanized, and more effective, for every elementary as pre-primary to eight-class students. MDM scheme is more relevant now to strengthen the Right to education act.

II. OBJECTIVES

- Improve learner's health, hygiene and good mental set.
- To improve quality education and well-being.
- To reduce drop-out and increase learners' attendance.
- Stop hunger, stop barriers and carry on education.

Statement of Problem

Specific problem or statement of the problem is a crucial stage of research. A study impact of Mid-day meal programme on academic achievement of pry. Education after the pandemic covid-19.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review is too much important to research. It means going through the previous researchers' findings related to or similar studies in the same field. The existence present study is a shortcoming of past studies. It helps to find new knowledge. The literature reviews are as bellow:

K.Anil Kumar(2021) has studied MDM and universal elementary education(U EE), and how it impacts education, academic achievement and holistic development of learners. Elementary Learners are provided free books, free uniforms, free shoes, and got cooked nutrition food for being successful UEE. Some parents do not show interest in their children's education during the financial crisis. Nowadays poor health and low nutrition become a barrier to education. That's why we allow social and financially weaker sections to strengthen UEE's vision and mission.

Kumar Swamy Vajja (2021) has posted in his study The Effectiveness of school health programme at the primary level that MDM is a factor in quality education. The primary level is time to build good character, morality and socialisation and holistic development. Subjective knowledge and practical knowledge is significant in making a nation. Quality education is enhanced by the mid-day meal.

Reetika Khara(2006) showed in his study that children in primary school are suffered due to malnutrition and illnesses. As a result of these, they give up education at the primary stage. Most of the parents lie below the poverty line (BPL) which consequence dropout, illiteracy and child labour. MDM is achieved through hot-cooked meals at lunch to the elementary stage for reducing the above malnutrition effects.

Jean Dreze et al have shown the Indian Govt nutrition support to all elementary students. Entertaining hot-cooked lunch has an impact on academic performance.

Dr S Kumar (Assistant prof of scert Delhi,2020) The researcher showed in his investigation of the mid-day meal scheme and its significance in the eradicating classroom that the students are providing one time a hot cooked meal is more beneficial for class after tiffin. Those children can't optimally learn who is hunger. In this context the NEP 2020 recommended it extend to not only preparatory stage but also implement in non Govt institute for quality education.

T.chakraborty and R. Jayraman have shown in their analysis the world' largest school feeding programme that impact on Scholastic and non scholastic performance. There are differences in learning capacity between the learner those who are take MDM and not take MDM.Hot clocks lunch in tiffin have positive effect on Reading, writing and learning progress.

MDM is now PM-POSHAN:After covid-19 MDM was humper. The government of India, collaborate with the state govt. And SHG(self-help group) NGOs are pushing the MDM schemes to reach the goal. 11.80 crore children and 11.20 lakh schools came under this initiative. Pradhan Mantri Poshan Shakti Nirman (PM-POSHAN)modified the version of the existing MDM scheme on 18th March 2018. This scheme is being implemented by the Ministry of Education and finally came to force on 1st April 2022. The Govt. of India spend about 24,400 crore Rupees every year on the scheme.

D. Sharma et al. (2021) have shown nationwide lockdown was declared and All educational institutes had been closed during the pandemic. The learner didn't go to the institute to learn. Every learner stress on online learning

rather than offline learning. In this scenario, a Mid-day meal played an important role in achieving academic goals.

K Deka (2021) conducted an assessment impact of the MDM scheme to increase attendance in primary education. Education makes an important role in breaking the poverty cycle and supporting hygiene. The Govt introduced the MDM scheme to increase attendance and quality education. The limited food resources are limited access to education. So, MDM has influenced academic achievement and attendance in schools.

IV. DATA COLLECTION

In the Coochbehar district, there are 1830 primary schools and 310 primary schools,17510 students come under the MDM scheme under Tufanganj subdivision juridical on. 25 schools and 500 students are selected through simple random during the 3 months. Primary data are collected from the result register, a record, opinions of Head Teachers, and different class teachers' experience with performance.

The data also collect from different cultures and The Sub Inspector of schools, articles and research papers.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The raw data are collected from summative evaluation records of individual students. The learner was awarded a grade point in 2007 and compared with awarded in 2021 grade at Tufanganj Sub-division in the Coochbehar district.

Table (1).Table(1) indicates the administered Alphabetically grade marks as distributed

Table (1):grade and marks distibution-

Grade	Marks
A.	80-100
B.	60-79
C.	45-59
D.	25-44
E.	Below 25

Table (2) shows the grade point awarded to primary students in class 1 to class 5. class and category-wise no. of students grade points awarded in 2007 before the MDM scheme implement.

Class	Grade A.	Grade B	Grade C	Grade D	Grade E.	Total students
Class1	10	22	15	38	15	100
Class2	12.	18	20	30	20	100
Class3	15	20	27	23	15	100
Class4	18	15	20	22	25	100
Class5	14	17	19	24	26	100
%	13.80%	18.40%	20.20%	27.40%	20.20%	500

Table (3) : class and category-wise no. of students grade points awarded in 2021. After the MDM scheme implement.

Class	Grade A	Grade B	Grade C	Grade D	Grade E	Total students
Class 1.	31.	25.	29	10	05	100
Class 2.	35	26.	19.	16.	04.	100
Class 3.	32.	21.	22.	20.	05.	100
Class 4.	30.	22.	19.	19.	10.	100
Class 5.	36.	21.	23.	12.	08.	100
%	32.8%	23%	22.70%	15.40%	6.40%	500

Table(3) shows the average grade point obtained by the primary students in classes 1 to 5 were class(1)-31%, class(2)-35%, class(3)-32%, class (4)-30%, class (5)36 % 'grade A' in 2021.

In 2021 after the implements MDM class wise grade points increased. The number of students who are graded 'A' increased after MDM was provided (32.8-13.8)% and the grade 'E' as a mark of poor comparatively decreased (20.2-6.4)%. These two tables (table-2 & table-3) showed that the classes one to five students achieved Grade-A, B & C for most of the students out of 500. So MDM becomes a factor to improve academic achievement.

VI. CONCLUSION

The observation, before and after providing MDM to primary students found that MDM has an incredible influence on academic achievement. MDM is the most government welfare scheme for nutrition support to primary students especially in poor rural areas. The data analysis clearly stated that the MDM is a factor that influence the academic achievement and it's more relevant after Covid-19.

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